

THE INTRODUCTION OF *AMICUS CURIAE* AS FORMAL LEGAL INSTRUMENT TO ENHANCE JUDICIAL INTEGRITY

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Abstract

The submission of Amicus Curiae's brief in the court has created a new paradigm that emerges and develops within the society itself. Such practice, which had already been developed in many judiciaries in other countries, could in fact be utilized by the Indonesian judiciary as a means to improve its integrity, namely by capturing the development of legal values and sense of justice within the society at large. Nevertheless, currently there have been no formal legal grounds to regulate the Amicus Curiae. Consequently, such condition has created confusion within those who presented themselves to become Amicus Curiae in the court. This paper intends to examine the possibility of formal recognition of Amicus Curiae as a full-fledged legal instrument in the court. Moreover, this paper also investigates various appropriate legal basis to accommodate the formal application of the Amicus Curiae in the court. Finally, this paper will endeavor to argue that the application of the Amicus Curiae as a formal legal instrument could be used by the Indonesian judiciary to enhance its integrity within the society itself.

Keywords: *Amicus Curiae, Legal Instrument, Judicial Integrity.*

Abstrak

Pengajuan surat Sahabat Pengadilan merupakan sebuah paradigma baru yang muncul dan berkembang di masyarakat. Praktik yang sudah lebih dahulu berkembang di banyak negara lain ini sesungguhnya dapat digunakan lembaga peradilan sebagai salah satu sarana untuk meningkatkan integritasnya, yaitu dengan menangkap perkembangan nilai hukum dan keadilan yang ada di masyarakat.

Namun demikian, saat ini belum ada ketentuan hukum yang mengatur secara formal hal tersebut. Hal ini menimbulkan kerancuan bagi masyarakat yang mengajukan diri sebagai Sahabat Pengadilan. Tulisan ini bertujuan untuk menelaah kemungkinan pengakuan formal Sahabat Pengadilan sebagai suatu instrumen hukum di pengadilan. Di samping itu, tulisan ini juga menyelidiki landasan hukum apa yang paling sesuai untuk mengakomodasi penerapan Sahabat Pengadilan tersebut. Pada akhirnya, tulisan ini akan mencoba memberikan argumentasi bahwa penerapan Sahabat Pengadilan sebagai pranata hukum sesungguhnya dapat digunakan lembaga peradilan Indonesia untuk meningkatkan integritasnya di masyarakat itu sendiri.

Keywords: Sahabat Pengadilan, Pranata Hukum, Integritas Peradilan.

Introduction

“Public opinion is always in advance of the law”

John Galsworthy¹

“The Law is good, if a man use it lawfully”

St. Timothy

Modern rule of law dictates prominent role in written legal provision to ensure the validity of legal act. In Indonesia, the affirmation of rule of law in the judiciary is expressed in the statement that the judiciary is independent to carry out its task of administering justice within the Indonesian rule of law.² Not only is any form of intervention to the judiciary from parties outside the court not permitted, it is also criminally punishable by law.³ In other words, the judicial independence is quintessential and needs to be safeguarded by the judges themselves.

It is curious to consider that there has been a captivating discussion regarding the role of civil society to express their view to the court or a judge hearing a case. Such practice is known as *Amicus Curiae*, a concept

¹ James Charlton, *Legal Briefs, A Lawyer's Quotation Book*, (New York: Mcgraw-Hill Publishing Company, 1990), p. 48.

² Article 1 paragraph 1 Law Number 48 Year 2009 on the Judiciary jo. article 24 paragraph (1) of the 1945 Indonesian Constitution.

³ Article 3 paragraph (2) Law Number 48 Year 2009 on the Judiciary.

derived from Latin language meaning “Friend of the Court”. For instance, on 14th April 2022, a coalition of civil societies consisting of groups of court observer, submitted their written comments to the court in their capacity of *Amicus Curiae* in the judicial review on the Ministry of Education and Culture Regulation Number 30 Year 2021 on the Prevention of Sexual Violence in Higher Education Institute.⁴ However, in spite of this novel development, the Indonesian procedural law still did not recognize the *Amicus Curiae* as a formal legal instrument in the court. The Law Number 8 of 1981 on the Criminal Procedural Law did not provide means for judge to include the *Amicus Curiae* in the considerations of their verdict. Nevertheless, this did not contradict the fact that there has already been many court verdicts which embraced the *Amicus Curiae* in their judgement.⁵

It is axiomatic that legal provisions often lag behind in keeping up with developments of the sense of justice within the society. A properly-functioning legal system also requires means that provide enough space for judge to adapt the application of legal provisions to ongoing societal development. Indonesian legal system has actually recognized this phenomenon by requiring judge to continually explore and grasp the legal values and sense of justice that develop in the society.

If such is the condition, could a recognition of the *Amicus Curiae* actually be one of the means which the court could utilize to stay current with the society’s legal development? Should it be the case, then what is the most appropriate legal instrument by which judge could implement it within the existing Indonesian legal framework? These questions will be the main topic of this writing, particularly as seen from the point of view of a first instance judge hearing criminal matter. Furthermore, such questions will also provide answer to the writer’s main argument, namely that insofar as conducted within the existing legal framework,

⁴ Asep Nursobah, “*Melalui Panitera MA, Koalisi Masyarakat Sipil Serahkan Amicus Curiae*”, Kepaniteraan Mahkamah Agung (19 April 2022), <https://kepaniteraan.mahkamahagung.go.id/registry-news/1977-melalui-panitera-ma-koalisi-masyarakat-sipil-serahkan-amicus-curiae>, accessed 28 February 2023.

⁵ Search results of keyword “*Amicus Curiae*” in the Indonesian Court Decision Directory (*Direktori Putusan*) indicates 27 judgments from 2008-2020 which included *Amicus Curiae* in its consideration, see https://putusan3.mahkamahagung.go.id/search.html?q=amicus+curiae&jenis_doc=&cat=&jd=&tp=&court=&put=&treg=&tupl=&tp=, accessed 28 February 2023.

the employment of Amicus Curiae could actually help in strengthening court's integrity in the midst of constant fluctuations of change in the society's conception of justice.

First Part: The Nature and Development of Amicus Curiae in Various Legal System

- The terminology of Amicus Curiae

Terminologically, Amicus Curiae derived from two Latin words, namely *Amicus* and *Curiae*. Amicus basically comes from the word “*Amice*”, meaning friendship or in a friendly manner,⁶ whereas *Curiae* derived from the word “*Curiae*” which signifies a building in which the senate met.⁷ In the course of time, Curiae did not only denote a place where a council routinely met, but also a place where judicial council held its hearing during the ancient Roman era.⁸ Thus, the combination of the words Amicus Curia could linguistically be defined as “Friend of the Court”.

The linguistic meaning of the word Amicus Curiae did not much differ with the definition given by present-day legal dictionaries. For instance, Oxford Dictionary of Law defines Amicus Curiae as a non-party who gives evidence to the court in order to aid judge in making arguments.⁹ Moreover, Merriam-Webster's Dictionary of Law describe it as a person (either an individual or entity) who is permitted to provide advice to court regarding certain issues relating to rules or facts in a lawsuit.¹⁰ Furthermore, Black's Law Dictionary,¹¹ defines it as a person not a party in a case who proposes or is asked by the court to propose

⁶ J.R.V. Marchant, M.A., *Cassell's Latin Dictionary, Latin-English and English-Latin*, (New York: Funk & Wagnalls Company, 1953), p. 35.

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ Mr S. J. Fockema Andreae, *Rechtsgeleerd Handwoordenboek, Verklaringen van Rechts en Bestuurstermen in Nederland Gebruikelijk, Voor Stude en Praktijk*, Second Edition, (Groningen, Djakarta: J.B. Wolters Uitgeversmaatschappij N.V., 1951, p. 82.

⁹ Jonathan Law (ed.), *A Dictionary of Law*, Eighth Edition, (Oxford: Oxford University Pers, 2015), p. 35.

¹⁰ Merriam-Webster, *Merriam-Webster's Dictionary of Law*, (Springfield, Massachusetts: Merriam Webster, Incorporated, 1996), p. 25.

¹¹ Bryan A. Garner (ed.), *Black's Law Dictionary*, Ninth Edition, (Texas: West Thomson Reuters, 2009), p. 98.

a letter because such person has a strong interest in a certain court case. In juridical literatures within the continental tradition, particularly the Dutch law, *Amicus Curiae* is generally known as the non-party third person (*derden*) who is given an opportunity to submit a relevant written information of his opinion (*relevante informatie of eigen inzichten*) regarding an ongoing court case to judge.¹² Meanwhile, French legal treatise refers *Amicus Curiae* to a subject who can be heard by judge in a civil case without requiring certain formalities (*peut entendre sans formalités*) with the aim of assisting the judge in obtaining certain information in the case.¹³

There is one similarity in the abovementioned definitions, namely that a party acting as an *Amicus Curiae* is not belonging to the one of the parties to a case. However, each dictionary differs in emphasizing the capacity of such party. Oxford Dictionary of Law regards it as a party who assists judge in investigating a case by means of providing them with additional evidence. Similarly, Merriam-Webster's Dictionary of Law sees it as a party who is allowed by the court to advise it in terms of certain norms or facts. Meanwhile, Black's Law Dictionary defines it as a party who has an interest in a case and can thus propose themselves or be asked by the court to propose themselves to be the Friend of the Court.

- The Historical Development of the *Amicus Curiae*

Various significations of the *Amicus Curiae* could actually be explained by inquiring upon the context of its initial conceptual development within the two main legal systems, namely the continental and Anglo-Saxon tradition. In this respect, a significant comprehension of the concept's initial application could hugely aid in examining the Friends of the Court's actual normative employment in the modern legal systems of other countries.

The Anglo-Saxon legal system primarily refers to a legal order that especially develops in various judicial institutions in English-speaking countries, whereas continental tradition focuses on written legal codes which contain detailed juridical norms regulating all aspects of human

¹² Rowie Stolk, et.al., "De *Amicus Curiae*: een instrument voor rechtsvorming of ook voor rechtsbescherming?", *Journal Ars Aequi*, vol. 68, no. 1 (2019), p. 9

¹³ Serge Braudo, "Définition de *Amicus curiae*", *Dictionnaire-juridique.com*, <https://www.dictionnaire-juridique.com/definition/amicus-curiae.php>, accessed 28 February 2023.

life.¹⁴ Yet, regardless of these signifying differences, the two traditions currently demonstrates a growing tendency to coalesce so that their contrast are no longer readily noticeable.¹⁵

First, Early Application of Amicus Curiae in the English law. Since its early inception in England, the Anglo-Saxon legal system grew out of the customary practice of English feudal society at that time.¹⁶ This usage then becomes an enduring tradition which is slowly recognized as possessing a distinct normative force by the court in its decision.¹⁷ Accordingly, such custom is formally recognized as a legal norm by the court. The conceptual development of the Amicus Curiae is thus formed against the backdrop of this court practice. Since the beginning of the fourteenth century, courts in England have been allowing bystanders who are not a party in a case, to appear to the court to advice judge regarding an alleged defects in an indictment with the aim of preventing the court from making mistakes in its decision.¹⁸ In fact, one of early functions of the Amicus Curiae was to notify the court of previous cases already decided upon which may not be known to the court presently hearing the case.¹⁹ Such role is known as “*Oral Shepardizing*”, in which court could obtain relevant references to arrive at consistent decisions in accordance with governing precedents.

The tradition dictates that a person acting as a Amicus Curiae is not formally required to be a jurist to the extent that he is demonstratively able to notice, inform, and caution the court examining a case. In this respect, the involvement of Amicus Curiae is admitted not only as a means for the court to be able to provide better decision so as to maintain the honor of the court, but also to keep abreast of ongoing

¹⁴ Raymond Wacks, *Law, A Very Short Introduction*, Second Edition, (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015), pp. 29-30.

¹⁵ Frederick Schauer, Civil Law, “Common law and the data of jurisprudence”, in *Common Law-Civil Law, The Great Divide?*, ed. by Nicoletta Bersier, (Cham: Springer, 2022), pp. 10-12.

¹⁶ Geoffrey Samuel, *A Short Introduction to the Common Law*, (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, 2013), p. 2.

¹⁷ *Idem*, h. 5.

¹⁸ S. Chandra Mohan, “The Amicus Curiae: Friends No More?”, *Singapore Journal of Legal Studies*, 2 (2010), p. 5.

¹⁹ Judithanne Scourfield McLauchlan, *Congressional Participation as Amicus Curiae before the U.S. Supreme Court*, (New York: LFB Scholarly Publishing LLC, 2005), pp. 3-4.

development in society's conception of justice so as to prevent judicial arbitrariness.

Second, Initial Implementation of *Amicus Curiae* in the continental tradition. In stark contrast to the tradition developed in the Anglo-Saxon legal system, legal evolution in countries embracing the continental tradition centered upon the comprehensive written legal provisions regulating all aspect of human life. In this fashion, the availability of distinctive group of legal scholars is indispensable to compile pertinent legal prescriptions and court decisions into an all-encompassing codification of law.²⁰ By so doing, the formation of law is thus far more centralized than what is the case in Anglo-Saxon countries which adopt a rather sporadic means to form the law.

The emergence of *Amicus Curiae* in the continental system is initially attributable to this context of legal formation. Aside from the presence of written legal compilations, early Roman court practice saw the incipient expansion of groups of jurist who originally did not necessarily possess formal legal qualifications.²¹ In this respect, a judge who is examining a case (*Praetor*) is effectively also a non-party third person appointed by litigating parties to examine and decide upon their case.²² In the execution of his duties, judge could ask for advice from a council, called *Consilium*, whose members are filled by well-versed legal scholars.²³ This particular council who in turn appears before the court as the judge's advisor to help him interpret the applicable norms.

Such participation of competent legal scholar in the court hearing plays a great role in the conceptual inception of *Amicus Curiae* within the Roman legal system, which would subsequently develop into the very roots of modern continental legal tradition espoused by many countries today. During the ancient Roman era, Friend of the Court was a person having established legal competent who could be requested by the court to help it in discovering the applicable law.²⁴ This historical

²⁰ George Mousourakis, *Roman Law and the Origins of the Civil Law Tradition*, (ChamL Springer International Publishing, 2015), p. 1.

²¹ Iryna Izarova, et.al., "Amicus curiae: origin, worldwide experience and suggestions for east european countries", *Hungarian Journal of Legal Studies*, vol. 60, no. 1 (2019), p. 22.

²² Iryna Izarova, et.al., "Amicus curiae: origin...", p. 23

²³ Iryna Izarova, et.al., "Amicus curiae: origin...", p. 23-24.

²⁴ Iryna Izarova, et.al., "Amicus curiae: origin...", p. 21.

background indicates that court still plays an essential role in deciding whether Amicus Curiae in the form of competent legal scholar may appear before the court to aid in finding the law.

- Normative Regulation of Amicus Curiae In Other Countries

First, the Employment of Amicus Curiae in the United States of America. As former colony of the British empire, the United States inherited Anglo Saxon legal tradition as reflected in various legal concepts that were integrated into the American society at the time.²⁵ Accordingly, court practice plays a critical role in interpreting and supervising the legal development itself.²⁶ Therefore, the American legal system could be representative example in examining the evolution of Friends of the Court in the Anglo-Saxon perspective.

The first use of Friends of the Court in the American court was formally recorded in 1823, in a land case in Kentucky between Green versus Biddle. A certain member of American congress by the name of Henry Clay submitted Amicus Curiae to the American Supreme Court to attract the court's attention to public interest which could be detrimentally affected by the said case.²⁷ Thereafter, the American Supreme Court issued an instruction in 1937, requiring Friends of the Court to obtain prior assent from the litigating parties in the case should it wishes to submit its brief to the court. Such instruction was nevertheless overruled afterwards by Supreme Court's instruction in 1949 which allows the submission of the Amicus brief without the litigating parties' prior consent, insofar as such submission was ordered by the court.²⁸

The distinct regulation of the Amicus brief was further provided by the Rule 37 of the Supreme Court Rules. Its first section states that the Amicus brief should pertinently indicate the matters asserted to be related to the case that have not previously been demonstrated by the litigating parties themselves. It states moreover that any Amicus brief

²⁵ G. Edward White, *American Legal History, A Very Short Introduction*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 2014, pp. 32, 47.

²⁶ Charles L. Zelden, *The American Judicial System, A Very Short Introduction*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 2022, p. 29.

²⁷ Samuel Krislov, "The Amicus curiae brief: from friendship to advocacy", *The Yale Law Journal*, vol. 72, no. 4 (1963), p. 700.

²⁸ Samuel Krislov, "The Amicus curiae...", p. 713.

failing to comply with such criteria was instead burdening the court. Also, an attorney having license to proceed before the United States Supreme Court must submit the Amicus brief in order for the brief to be valid.²⁹

Whilst the second section of the said provision states furthermore that Amicus Curiae has to first obtain written consent from parties to a case before submitting Amicus brief, it could be set aside by the Amicus Curiae should it fails to obtain the assent. In such circumstance, the Amicus Curiae has to submit a motion for leave to the court asking permission to deviate from the required procedure. In that event, the submitted Amicus brief has to include the name of the party who disagree with its involvement, along with the description of the Amicus Curiae's interest.

Viewed from the American context, Amicus Curiae is effectively an interested non-party third person, who acts in support of one of the parties to the case. The norms implemented by the United States Supreme Court in 1946 in the *Universal Oil Products versus Root Refrigerating Co.*, case has in fact shifted the paradigm of Amicus Curiae in the United States from the practice that exists in the Anglo-Saxon legal system generally. The nature of Amicus Curiae has transformed from previously upholding "neutrality" to "partiality", and from "friendship" to "advocacy".³⁰

Second, the Employment of Friends of the Court in the Netherland. The Dutch legal system basically adopts continental tradition that gives prominence to the written legal prescription. It saw great influence from the French law with the introduction of the Napoleonic code (*Code Civil*) at the beginning of the nineteenth century which had left indelible imprint in the Netherland. Consequently, Dutch legal system has a comprehensive codification which becomes judge's main reference in discovering as well as interpreting the law.³¹ Such

²⁹ Legal Information Institute, "Rule 37. Brief for an Amicus Curiae", *aw.cornell.edu*, https://www.law.cornell.edu/rules/supct/rule_37, accessed 2 March 2023.

³⁰ Padideh Ala'i, "Judicial lobbying at the WTO: the debate over the use of amicus briefs and the U.S. experience", *Fordham International Law Journal*, Vol. 24, No. 1 (2000), p. 87.

³¹ J.M.J. Chorus, "History", in *Introduction to Dutch Law*, ed. by Jeroen Chorus, (Alphen aan den Rijn: Kluwer Law International B.V., 2016), p. 12.

strong emphasis to the written norm is, therefore, the main feature of the evolution of Amicus Curiae in the Netherland.

In contrast to the formal recognition of Amicus Curiae in the United States, the Dutch legal system did not formally acknowledge it as a proper legal concept. This condition is due to the fact that the Dutch procedural law principally did not admit third party to intervene in the judicial process. Initially, the provision whose implementation closely resembles Amicus Curiae, namely by allowing third party's entrance to submit their opinion, is article 44a of Dutch Civil Procedural Code (*Wetboek van Burgerlijke Rechtsvordering*).³² This article governs the mechanism wherein Dutch Competition Supervisory Body (*Autoriteit Consument & Markt*) and European Commission could submit their request to judge to be allowed to submit its written opinion in a commercial competition case (*mededigingsrechtelijke procedures*). If the court approve their request, these two entities would then appear before the court not as parties proper to the case, but as third party who could be permitted to provide their oral opinion relating to the case.³³

Nevertheless, Dutch legal academia are beginning to discuss the potentiality of adopting Amicus Curiae as a full-fledged legal instrument which could contribute in the formation of law itself, particularly in a case involving public at large.³⁴ Without particularly excluding judge's main role in discovering the law through various normative technique, there has been suggestion to sanctioning the employment of Amicus Curiae in certain cases, albeit with strict conditions (*in bijzondere gevallen en onder strikte voorwaarden*).

In the report of the Dutch State Council (*Raad van State*) on the potential application of the Amicus Curiae in Dutch administrative court, it is suggested that judge's principal role in the formation of law could still not be negated. However, it ought to be realized that it is the judge's very nature to specifically decide upon particular case by

³² George Cumming and Mirjam Freudenthal. *Civil Procedure in EU Competition Cases Before the English and Dutch Courts*, (Alphen aan den Rijn: Kluwer Law International B.V., 2010), p. 172.

³³ See the provisions of *Wetboek van Burgerlijke Rechtsvordering* in "Wetboek van Burgerlijke Rechtsvordering (geldt in geval van digitaal procederen)", [wetten.overheid.nl](https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0001827/2023-01-01), <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0001827/2023-01-01>, accessed 2 March 2023.

³⁴ T. Barkhuysen, "Betere bestuursrechtelijke rechtsvorming met een Amicus Curiae", *Nederlands Juristen Blad*, 2014/519, Aflevering 10 (2014), p. 633.

restricting himself within the individuality of the case being examined (*casusgerichtheid*).³⁵ Accordingly, judge's limitative propensity turns out to be an encumbrance since he is effectively discouraged to consider the attendant effect of his decision to the community. To prevent such eventuality, the opinion presented by Amicus Curiae could support judge in making decision that also taking into account the much larger effect (*macroevolgen*) of his decision. Thus, the formation of law by means of judicial decision could achieve far greater legitimacy (*legitimiteit van rechtsvorming*).³⁶

The academic's proposal and the State Council's report sparked agitated debates on the formal employment of Amicus Curiae in Dutch court which subsequently leads to the proposed revision of the State Administration Law (*Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht*) in Dutch parliament.³⁷ This proposal is widely known as the bill of the Amicus Curiae and Cross Appointments (*wetsvoorstel amicus curiae en kruisbenoemingen*).³⁸ Moreover, the Dutch Supreme Court also welcomed the possibility of employing Amicus Curiae as part of its entire effort to create legal unity and improve the quality of law formation.³⁹ The Explanatory Memorandum (*Memorie van Toelichting*) of the proposed bill on the revision of *Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht* mentioned furthermore that Amicus Curiae could be a judicial instrument to obtain a complete picture of not only juridical, but also societal aspect of a case. It is, thus, expected to support judge in answering legal questions whose scope

³⁵ Prof. mr. J.C.A. de Poorter, et.al., "De Amicus curiae geëvalueerd", (Den Haag: Afdeling Bestuursrechtspraak van de Raad van State, 2019), p. 24.

³⁶ Prof. mr. J.C.A. de Poorter, et.al., "De Amicus...", p. 25.

³⁷ Tom Barkhuysen, "De Amicus Curiae in het Bestuursrecht Wettelijk Verankerd bij Hamerstuk", *Stibbe.com* (23 October 2020), <http://www.stibbeblog.nl/all-blog-posts/environment-and-planning/de-amicus-curiae-in-het-bestuursrecht-wettelijk-verankerd-bij-hamerstuk/>, accessed 2 March 2023.

³⁸ Rijksoverheid, "Nader Rapport Wetsvoorstel Amicus Curiae en Kruisbenoemingen", *Rijksoverheid.nl* (20 August 2020), <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2020/08/20/tk-nader-rapport-inzake-het-voorstel-van-wet-amicus-curiae-en-kruisbenoemingen>, accessed 3 March 2023.

³⁹ Hoge Raad der Nederlanden, "Consultatieadvies Hoge Raad der Nederlanden", *Rijksoverheid.nl*, <https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/blg-944490.pdf>, accessed 2 March 2023.

goes beyond the particular interest of parties to the case (*boven de specifieke belangen van procespartijen*).⁴⁰

The proposed bill enabling the employment of Amicus Curiae in Dutch administrative court was eventually accepted by the Dutch parliament as Law of 14 October 2020 (*Wet van 14 Oktober 2020*), which was promulgated in the State Gazette Number (*Staatsblad*) 416 year 2020 of 4 November 2020.⁴¹ The law changed at the same time not only the state administration law, but also the judiciary, and state tax collection.⁴² Moreover, it also added new provision in the Dutch Administrative Law (*Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht*), namely article 8:12b, whose first section states that administrative court could allow non-party third person to submit their written opinion within the timeframe decided by the panel of judges.⁴³ Curiously, the third section states that the initiative to allow the third party's entrance shall come from the presiding judge after first hearing the litigating parties' response.⁴⁴ In addition, they are also given the occasion to express their view on the allowed third party's opinion.⁴⁵ The panel of judges may also invite the Amicus Curiae to further clarify points of arguments in their submitted written opinion.⁴⁶

⁴⁰ Rijksoverheid, "Memorie van Toelichting Wetsvoorstel Amicus Curiae en Kruisbenoemingen", *Rijksoverheid.nl* (20 August 2020), <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2020/08/20/tk-nader-rapport-inzake-het-voorstel-van-wet-amicus-curiae-en-kruisbenoemingen>, accessed 3 March 2023.

⁴¹ The complete name of this Dutch law (*wet*) is *Wet van 14 oktober 2020 tot wijziging van de Algemene wet bestuursrecht, de Algemene wet inzake rijksbelastingen, de Wet op de rechterlijke organisatie en de Wet rechtspositie rechterlijke ambtenaren in verband met enkele wijzigingen in het belang van de rechtseenheid en de rechtsontwikkeling bij de hoogste rechtscolleges (amicus curiae en kruisbenoemingen)*.

⁴² See moreover the complete provisions of *Wet van 14 oktober 2020* in Staatsblad van het Koninkrijk der Nederlanden, "Wet van 14 oktober 2020 tot wijziging van de Algemene wet bestuursrecht, de Algemene wet inzake rijksbelastingen, de Wet op de rechterlijke organisatie en de Wet rechtspositie rechterlijke ambtenaren in verband met enkele wijzigingen in het belang van de rechtseenheid en de rechtsontwikkeling bij de hoogste rechtscolleges (amicus curiae en kruisbenoemingen)", *zoek.officiëlebekendmakingen.nl*, <https://zoek.officiëlebekendmakingen.nl/stb-2020-416.pdf>, accessed 3 March 2023.

⁴³ Artikel 8:12b paragraph 1 Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht.

⁴⁴ Artikel 8:12b paragraph 3 Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht.

⁴⁵ Artikel 8:12b paragraph 4 Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht.

⁴⁶ Artikel 8:12b paragraph 5 Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht.

- Divergence in Legal Tradition with regard to the Implementation of Amicus Curiae

Examination into the Amicus Curiae's application in two countries which adheres to significantly different legal system, namely the United States with Anglo-Saxon legal tradition, and the Netherlands with continental legal tradition, demonstrates essential differences in the evolution of Amicus Curiae as a legal instrument. Distinctive historical progress within each tradition practically illustrates Amicus Curiae's conceptual evolution.

In principle, American court plays a primary role in creating rules and norms on the employment of Amicus Curiae which cannot be detached from the fact that the United States Supreme Court has a particularly greater space to actively determine the direction of legal development⁴⁷ In this regard, Federal Judiciary Act 1789 allows the American judiciary to create regulation necessary *for the orderly conducting business in the said courts*, insofar as not conflicting with the existing regulations.⁴⁸ Some of these norms are subsequently codified in regulations and instructions governing procedure in the court (*Rules and Guidance*). In addition to the Supreme Court's Rules Number 37, which regulates the Amicus Curiae, the United State Supreme Court issues instruction concerning the submission of the Amicus brief in the court (*Guide to Filing Amicus Curiae Briefs*).⁴⁹

In contrast, the Dutch law highlights the importance of written code issued by competent body having the authority to promulgate such law.⁵⁰ It put into practice long established tradition of law-making

⁴⁷ Linda Greenhouse, *The U.S. Supreme Court, A Very Short Introduction*, (New York, Oxford University Press, 2012, pp. 47, 91-93.

⁴⁸ See moreover the complete text of Federal Judiciary Act (1789) in National Archives, "Federal Judiciary Act (1789)", *archives.gov* (10 May 2022), <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/federal-judiciary-act>, accessed 4 March 2023.

⁴⁹ Supreme Court of the United States, "Rules and Guidance", *Supremecourt.gov*, https://www.supremecourt.gov/filingandrules/rules_guidance.aspx, accessed 4 March 2023.

⁵⁰ The central role of Dutch judges could not be separated from their main task, which is to implement and maintain people's rights and obligations. See Mr. drs. F.J.P. Lock, *Burgerlike Procesrecht*, (Den Haag: Boom Juridisch, 2020), p. 9.

through the intermediary of learned scholars who formulate law in a centralized fashion which will subsequently be applied by the court. This way of law-making through a structured and methodical manner starting from the debate of draft law in the parliament to the eventual revision of old laws is squarely reflected in how the Netherland was finally able to formally adopt Amicus Curiae in Article 44a of Civil Procedural Code (*Wetboek van Burgerlijke Rechtsvordering*) and Article 8:12b of State Administration Law (*Algemene Wet Bestuursrecht*).

Such structured method by means of legislation is also applied by various other countries that traditionally adhere to the continental legal system. In 1999 Brazil enacted a law which incorporated Amicus Curiae in the Brazilian constitutional court. In similar fashion, Argentinian and Peruvian parliament also adopted Amicus Curiae. In Europe, France amended in 2010 its law on administrative justice to formally allow the implementation of Amicus Curiae.⁵¹

Second: Amicus Curiae as a Form of Court Enterprise in Keeping Abreast of Legal Development

Examination of Amicus Curiae's long development within two main legal systems as well as its normative provision in the American and Dutch law has provided us with a solid theoretical and comparative foundation to comprehend its nature. At present, we will see whether this comparative insight could help in investigating the possibility of formally introducing Amicus Curiae in Indonesia.

- Early Implementation and the Court's Reaction

It is interesting to observe that Amicus Curiae has in fact been employed in the Indonesian court for quite a long time already. The very first recorded instance of Amicus brief submission to the Indonesian court is in a civil case between Soeharto versus Time Magazine in 2008. In addition to numerous local media and journalist organizations,⁵² the Amicus brief was also submitted by 23 non-

⁵¹ Steven Kochevar, "Amici Curiae in civil law jurisdictions", *Yale Law Journal*, Vol. 122 (2013), pp. 1661-1662.

⁵² Institute for Criminal Justice Reform, "Amicus Curiae Time vs. Soeharto", *icjr.or.id* (22 February 2012), <https://icjr.or.id/amicus-curiae-time-vs-soeharto/>, accessed 4 March 2023.

government organizations and foreign media, to the panel of judges who was at that time examining a judicial review on the court case number 3215 K/Pdt/2001 on 30 August 2007. The brief was intended to help reminding the judges on the attendant effect of their decision on press freedom and journalism in Indonesia.⁵³

This early employment of Amicus brief inevitably sparked numerous reactions from the public. Some considered its submission as a celebrated innovation in the Indonesian court practice, whereas others regarded a non-party third person's entrance into a case other than third party lawsuit known colloquially as *derden verzet*, as unrecognized in the provisions of procedural law, and thus undesired.⁵⁴

Since the submission of the said Amicus brief, public awareness of the novel practice's availability and potential began to emerge. Not only was it used in the aforementioned civil case, but also in a great deal of other cases. Scores of groups began advocating the use of Amicus brief in cases which had garnered considerable public attention. For instance, a coalition of civil societies submitted Amicus brief in October 2009 to the panel of judges examining Prita Mulyasari criminal case Number 1269/Pid.B/2009/PN. Tng in the Tangerang District Court.⁵⁵ In the same way, four coalition of civil societies put forward an amicus brief to the Kupang District Court in Reyndhart R.N. Siahaan's special criminal case in case number 83/Pid.Sus/2020/PN. Kpg.⁵⁶ Likewise, a group of non-governmental organizations proposed the brief in the judicial review of the Semarang State Administrative Court's Decision number 64/G/2015/PTUN. Smg.⁵⁷

⁵³ Pernyataan Para Teman (Amici Curiae) Untuk Mendukung Permohonan Peninjauan Kembali, <https://icjrid.files.wordpress.com/2012/02/scan001.pdf>, accessed 4 March 2023.

⁵⁴ Ali, "Amicus Curiae Dipakai Membantu Permohonan PK", *bukumonline.com* (12 August 2008), <https://www.hukumonline.com/berita/a/iamicus-curiae-dipakai-membantu-permohonan-pk--hol19896?page=1>, accessed 4 March 2023.

⁵⁵ Amicus Curiae (Komentar Tertulis), https://icjrid.files.wordpress.com/2009/10/prita_brief.pdf, accessed 4 March 2023.

⁵⁶ Institute for Criminal Justice Reform (ICJR), "Amicus Curiae (Sahabat Pengadilan) untuk Majelis Hakim Perkara No.83/Pid.Sus/2020/PN. Kpg", *leip.or.id* (June 2020), https://leip.or.id/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/ICJR-IJRS-LBHM-LeIP-Amicus-RR-PN-Kpg_upload.pdf, accessed 4 March 2023.

⁵⁷ Amicus Curiae Atas Peninjauan Kembali Terkait Putusan Pengadilan Tata Usaha Negara (PTUN) Semarang No. 064/G/2015/PTUN.SMG (Joko Prianto dkk. v. I.

This phenomenon reflects a new paradigm, which is the ever-increasing public awareness on the Amicus Curiae's role. Categorically, the submission of an Amicus brief was not intended to put inappropriate influence in the shape of public pressure upon judge, but instead to help him in investigating the subject matter in a rather broader context so that his decision could holistically be in accordance with sense of justice in the community.⁵⁸ Its teleological essence could thus be found in the public interest which may be eventually affected by court decision.⁵⁹

Despite such progress, court itself has showed circumspection with regard to the submission of Amicus brief. For example, in one criminal case, a panel of judges has allowed the submission of Amicus brief as part of the litigant's motion, but refused nevertheless to include it in the consideration part of their judgment.⁶⁰ Similarly, one panel of judges did not put the Amicus brief in their consideration, stating that the standard format of sentencing as regulated in the Article 197 of the Code of Criminal Procedure did not require judges to include Amicus brief.⁶¹ Since it could only serve as ancillary information for the judge, the Amicus Curiae's opinions is in no way binding the judge in his decision.

- Amicus Curiae as a Form of Judicial Enterprise to Keeping Abreast with Legal Development in the Society

Multiple reactions,⁶² to the introduction of the Amicus Curiae practically constitutes a phenomenon of the increasing proliferation of

Gubernur Jawa Tengah; II. PT. Semen Gresik) dan Putusan Pengadilan Tinggi Tata Usaha Negara Surabaya No. 135/B/2015/PT.TUN.SBY, <https://herlambangperdana.files.wordpress.com/2008/07/amicus-curiae-rembang-2016.pdf>, accessed 4 March 2023.

⁵⁸ Amicus Curiae Atas Peninjauan Kembali..., p.1.

⁵⁹ Siti Aminah, *Menjadi Sababat Pengadilan, Panduan Menyusun Amicus Brief*, (Jakarta: The Indonesian Legal Resource Center (ILRC), 2014), p. 13.

⁶⁰ For example the Medan Hight Court Decision (*Putusan Pengadilan Tinggi Medan*) Number 1495/Pid.Sus/2020/PT Mdn on 12 November 2020 and the Indonesian Supreme Court Decision (*Putusan Mahkamah Agung Republik Indonesia*) Number 1172K/Pid/2015 on 23 December 2015.

⁶¹ The Batulicin District Court Decision (*Putusan Pengadilan Negeri Batulicin*) Number 268/Pid.B/2021/ PN Bln on 14 February 2022.

⁶² Arthur Selwyn Miller, "Public confidence in the judiciary: some notes and reflections", *Judicial Ethics*, vol. 35, no.1 (1970), p. 69.

community's interest and concern for judicial role carried out by judge. Increase of visibility of judicial duties could have an effect upon the level of the court's public confidence.⁶³ Nevertheless, this brings the court in an ambivalent stature. On the one hand, the judiciary, being part of the overarching state power, is naturally not immune from critics, commentaries, and opinions from the public, but on the other hand, the space in which the court could response to such criticisms and thereby influence its public perception is strictly restricted.

Amidst this backdrop, the court has to decide upon its position on the nature of Amicus brief whose content in essence also captures these ongoing opinions and commentaries that had been developing within the society. Historical examination of its long history in the United States and the Netherland as previously elaborated, indicate that Friend of the Court could hugely contribute to the development of law.⁶⁴ Its proper employment in the court may moreover assist the court in sustaining the legal unity itself.⁶⁵ By the same token, the effectivity of court decision could distinctly be augmented to a great extent since an Amicus brief must necessarily reflect the opinion current in the society at the time of the verdict. By and large, these developments could certainly add on public acceptance of court judgments.

For the same reason, the existence of civil societies with increasing awareness of their interest which could span beyond the interest of the litigants, could simply not be disregarded by the court.⁶⁶ Since court may be unaware of this interest, the Amicus brief could promptly inform the court regarding such information, such as in the environment or human right cases.

Yet, it is crucial to maintain that Amicus brief could and should not be the only means for judge to answer particular legal matters. Such task

⁶³ Raymond J. Lohier JR, et. al., "Losing faith, why public distrust in the judiciary matters and what judges can do about it", *Judicature*, vol. 106, no. 2 (2022), p. 71.

⁶⁴ Mr. A.J.C. Perdaems, "Vriend Van De Hoge Raad Roept Veel Vragen Op", *advocatenblad.nl* (3 August 2021) <https://www.advocatenblad.nl/2021/08/03/vriend-van-de-hoge-raad-roept-veel-vragen-op/>, accessed 5 March 2023.

⁶⁵ T. Barkhuysen dan N. Jak, "De Amicus curiae in het bestuursrecht wettelijk verankerd: experimenten maar!", *Nederlands Tijdschrift voor Bestuursrecht*, vol. 20, no. 7 (2020), p. 368.

⁶⁶ Ruben J. Garcia, "A Democratic theory of amicus advocacy", *Florida State University Law Review*, vol. 35, no. 2 (2008), pp. 340-342.

is the sole domain of judge's authority which cannot be violated at any means by any party. The Amicus brief's role should thereby be restricted in only providing judges with non-judicial information which may appertain to public interest at large. The lawmaker has to consider this limitation in formulating appropriate space in which Friend of the Court may legally put forward their opinion in accordance with the existing formal legal provisions.

In a democratic rule of law setting, the concept of court integrity acquires its new dynamic, namely the relationship between judicial accountability and public trust, which puts strong emphasis on external accountability of the judiciary⁶⁷. Similarly, the legitimacy of judicial institution is factually depended among others on the public confidence. The concept of judicial independence and its accountability become closely intertwined one another.⁶⁸

Amicus Curiae has thus a role which could have a positive bearing on the judicial institution. Not only could it provide valuable assistance to the court in considering as much variables as possible that could surface in a case, but also in keeping current with the evolution of values and paradigm in the community. In this respect, court could obtain far broader legitimacy in the society. Therefore, the Writer is of the opinion that Amicus Curiae could be utilized as one of formal legal instruments to achieve that goal.

In any case, norms regulating court task ought to be formulated in a distinct and written legal provisions that can be known by all parties. The Dutch experience teaches us that Amicus Curiae could be inserted within the overall judicial procedure by means of a structured legislative deliberation. This could be an invaluable reference to Indonesian lawmaker opting to attain the same aim. Despite its potential as an additional means to support court task, its insertion within the Indonesian legal system should also be carried out by means of distinctive legal provisions, which is the appropriate implementation of legal adage quoted at the beginning of this writing, namely that *The Law is good, if a man use it lawfully*.

⁶⁷ Jonathan Soeharno, *The Integrity of the Judge, A Philosophical Inquiry*, (Surrey: Ashgate Publishing Limited, 2009) p. 23.

⁶⁸ Peter Hack, "Introduction judicial integrity", in *Judicial Integrity*, ed. by Andras Sajo (Leiden: Koninklijke Brill NV, 2004), pp. 11-12.

Third: Legal Arrangements as Normative Basis for Implementing Amicus Curiae

- Ambiguity in the Legal Basis used by the Friends of the Court

In general, most of the Amicus briefs presented to the court has invoked article 5 paragraph 1 Law Number 48 of 2009 regarding the Judiciary to legitimize its submission to court. The article is essentially a provision dictating judge to constantly explore, follow, and understand the sense of justice in the society. For example, one Amicus brief opined that judges should be aware of the input brought by all parties to better understand the importance of the matter they examine because such information would prove valuable to judge making his judgment.⁶⁹

Such statement necessarily prompts one to investigate whether the said provision could be referred to as a solid basis for approving the entrance of Amicus Curiae. Historically, article 5 paragraph (1) of the said provision regulates the very same norm that has been previously given by article 27 paragraph (1) Law Number 14 of 1970 regarding the Judiciary, which put a slightly different formulation, namely “as a law enforcer who decides upon a case, judge has to follow and understand the sense of justice living in the society”.⁷⁰ The elucidation section of the article states that “In a society that still espouses unwritten legal norms in a period of upheaval and transition, judges are the creator and explorer of legal values living among the people”. It further formulates that “he (the judge) has to immerse himself in life of the people in order to be able to become acquainted with their legal feeling and sense of justice”. In this way, judge could give decision in accordance with both the law and the society’s sense of justice”.⁷¹

⁶⁹ Siti Aminah, *Menjadi Sahabat Pengadilan...*, pp. 13-14.

⁷⁰ The original Indonesian text reads: “*hakim sebagai penegak hukum dan keadilan wajib mengadili, mengikuti, dan memahami nilai-nilai hukum yang hidup di masyarakat*”.

⁷¹ The original Indonesian text reads: “*Dalam masyarakat yang masih mengenal hukum tidak tertulis, serta berada dalam masa pergolakan dan peralihan, Hakim merupakan perumus dan penggali dari nilai-nilai hukum yang hidup di kalangan rakyat. Ia harus terjun ke tengah-tengah masyarakat untuk mengenal, merasakan dan mampu menyelami perasaan hukum dan rasa keadilan yang hidup dalam masyarakat. Dengan demikian Hakim dapat memberikan putusan yang sesuai dengan hukum dan rasa keadilan masyarakat*”.

Over the course of time, similar formulations were also adopted in article 28 paragraph (1) Law Number 4 of 2004 regarding the Judiciary, albeit with briefer elucidation, namely that court decision has to be in accordance with the law and the society's sense of justice. This formulation and elucidation would thereafter be adopted by the present article 5 paragraph (1) Law Number 48 of 2009 on the Judiciary.

The provision's long history demonstrates that lawmaker has put strong emphasis to highlight the importance of instinctively finding and exploring ongoing norms and feeling of justice within the society. Consequently, judge should be able to proactively discover norms that has not only been contained in legal stipulations, but also in society.⁷² To put it another way, judge should creatively exercise law finding and law making. Therefore, he could not decide himself incompetent or incapable on the pretext of the supposed insufficiency or uncertainty in existing regulations.

This is precisely the meaning of judge's obligation to explore sense of justice living in the society. Such rule is closely related to provisions in article 10 paragraph (1) Law Number 48 of 2009 regarding the Judiciary, which proscribe judge to decline to examine a case for reasons of alleged uncertainty or unavailability of regulations. In contrast, provision dictating him to constantly investigate sense of justice flourishing in the community shows that judge may and should make creative use of numerous juridical methods of legal finding and legal forming so that he could adjudicate and resolve cases brought to him.

Furthermore, article 2 and 3 Law Number 48 of 2009 regarding the Judiciary give prominence to the independence of judicial institution from all forms of intervention.⁷³ Accordingly,⁷⁴ judge is bound to implement positive norms which provide him with a certain normative

⁷² Dr. Ismail Rumadan, M.H., *Laporan Penelitian Makna Menggali dan Mengikuti Nilai-nilai Hukum dan Rasa Keadilan yang Hidup dalam Masyarakat Terkait dengan Kewenangan Hakim Memeriksa dan Memutuss Perkara Perdata*, (Megamendung: Puslitbang Hukum dan Peradilan Badan Litbang Diklat Kumdil Mahkamah Agung Republik Indonesia, 2016), pp. 1-2.

⁷³ Dr. H. Boy Nurdin, S.H., M.H. *Kedudukan dan Fungsi Hakim dalam Penegakan Hukum di Indonesia*, (Bandung: Penerbit P.T. Alumni, 2012) p. 133.

⁷⁴ Dr. Dahlan Sinaga, S.H., M.H., *Kemandirian dan Kebebasan Hakim Memutus Perkara Pidana dalam Negara Hukum Pancasila, Suatu Perspektif Teori Keadilan Bermartabat*, (Bandung: CV. Hikam Media Utama, 2020), p. 20.

sphere. This means that he should be neutral not only of the litigants interests whose case he examines, but also all other parties endeavoring to influence his decision.

It is now evident that the essence of judge duty to discover sense of justice as given in article 5 paragraph (1) Law Number 48 of 2009 differs essentially with the argumentations brought forward by various Amicus brief to legitimize their position. The provision in that article was primarily intended to encourage judge to actively discover substantive norms related to the case, and thus not to formally create new procedural instrument to accept the employment of Amicus brief in the court. Therefore, it is has to be admitted that there has still been no explicit legal bases to formally employ Amicus Curiae within the Indonesian court procedure.

- Future Regulation of Amicus Curiae in the Court

It is evident that the actual Indonesian legal system lacks normative provisions governing the use of Amicus Curiae. This has to be properly realized by all parties, particularly those employing the Amicus Curiae. If it is to be acknowledged as a proper mean to empower the court's integrity, it needs to be adequately regulated in a distinctive rule to prevent its utilization in unrestrained manner. Taking the above comparative discourse into account, the Writer offers two alternative arrangements, namely regulation through the supreme court as is the case in the United States or regulation by means of legislation as in the Netherland.

First, regulation by the Supreme Court. In accordance with the article 79 Law Number 14 of 1985 regarding the Judiciary as amended by Law Number 5 of 2004 and Law Number 3 of 2009, the Indonesian Supreme Court can provide further regulation on matters necessary for the smooth running of the justice system if such matters are not sufficiently regulated in the provision of law. Its elucidation part states that in the event of the paucity or even absence of regulation, the Supreme Court has the authority to issue its own regulation to fill them.

In practice, the Supreme Court makes active use of this regulating authority to fill nonregulation in procedural domain by means of the issuance of the Supreme Court circular letter and regulation. This kind

of authority, which does not even exist in the Dutch Supreme Court,⁷⁵ has been implemented, to a large extent, by the Indonesian Supreme Court to maintain the unity of law and its application in the judicial institutions below it.⁷⁶ In this respect, the Indonesian Supreme Court could take a step forward in regulating the employment of Amicus Curiae with the help of the Supreme Court Regulation. Such regulation will govern its intricate technicalities, such as parties who can act as Amicus Curiae along with their requirements, in which case such parties could appear to present their Amicus brief, the permissible timing of their appearance, the main litigating parties' consent, and so forth. In this fashion, the Indonesian Supreme Court could fill the gap of actual nonregulation of Amicus Curiae, thus providing legal certainty with regard to the practice of Amicus Curiae in the Indonesian court.

Second, legislation. As in the Netherland, legislation will ensure the process of establishing Amicus Curiae as a legal institution in a more structured and methodical manner. However, this undertaking requires a rather long time and discussion. There needs to be initial initiative from the legislative or executive body to propose it as a bill to revise the existing criminal or civil procedural code. Moreover, all interested parties who would later implement such provisions such as civil societies, legal academics, and the judiciary, have to be invited to offer their thought thereon. This legislative mechanism would generally involve a lengthy debates before it finally become a law.

By and large, the Writer opine that the first method, namely the regulation by the Indonesian Supreme Court, would provide greater certainty and convenience, compared to regulatory method through the legislation. The Indonesian Supreme Court could make the first move more quickly by further regulating the nature and application of the Amicus Curia as formal legal instrument in the court. Therefore, its use could have a positive impact on the integrity of the judiciary in a way that does not contradict the governing provision of law.

⁷⁵ Marjanne Termorshuizen-Arts, "Revisie en herziening, de continuïteit in de indonesische rechtspleging", *Bijdragen tot de Taal, Land en Volkenkunde*, deel 150, afl. 2 (1994), p. 336.

⁷⁶ Marjanne Termorshuizen-Arts, "Revisie...", p. 334. See also the history of this regulating authority in Cornelis Paulus Briët, *Het Hooggerechts Hof van Nederlands-Indië 1819 - 1848 Portret van een Vergeten Rechtscollege*, (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Pers B.V., 2015), pp. 144-148.

Conclusion

The Amicus Curia as a new paradigm that emerges and develops in the society is a phenomenon which should not be simply put aside by the court. In essence, it is a form of public participation to improve the integrity of the judiciary. Judge could make use of information provided by the Amicus Curiae to keep up current with the development of legal values and sense of justice in the society. Moreover, experiences gained from its application in other countries demonstrate that Amicus Curiae could be a means for the court to strengthen its legitimation in the society. The court could capture these development to anticipate the impact of the court's decision on the public at large. All of this encourages many countries to confer formal legal recognition to the implementation of Amicus Curiae.

Yet, the actual Amicus Curiae's nonregulation in Indonesia leads to unrestrained and unfounded use in practice. The Indonesian Supreme Court could in fact play an active role in maintaining legal certainty by providing further necessary regulations on the employment of Amicus Curiae in the court. In this fashion, the Indonesian Supreme Court could make it an advantageous means to improve the integrity of the judiciary which ultimately aid in realizing public civility in the execution of its duties.

While legal development in the society would invariably precede that in the provision of law, it still has to be done in accordance with the governing procedure set by the law. The same is also the case with regard to the employment of Amicus Curiae. If it is set to contribute in improving the integrity of judiciary, it has to be regulated in accordance with the procedure set by the law.

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